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A NOVEL CYLINDRICAL GATE ALL AROUND MOSFET USING INAS AS CHANNEL AND HfO₂ AS GATE OXIDE

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Abstract:

Recently InAs-based MOSFETs draw the researchers' attention owing to their improved overall performance over their Si-based counterparts. Suitable high-k dielectrics such as Al₂O₃, HfO₂ etc. are proposed as gate oxide to further enhance their performances. Such combinations (InAs-based channel and high-k dielectrics as gate oxide) are investigated in the literature for the single-gate to multiple gate MOSFETs, but not for the Gate-All-Around (GAA) MOSFETs. This work aims to make an investigative performance evaluation for an InAs/ HfO₂-based cylindrical GAA MOSFET. In doing so, a GAA structure is proposed with InAs as the nanowire material and HfO₂ as gate oxide material. Improved results in the various aspects such as the maximum current, inverse sub-threshold slope and maximum transconductance in comparison with InAs/SiO₂ and Si/SiO₂-based GAA structures show that the proposed combination possesses a great promise in the future high-performance MOSFETs.

Key words: Gate All Around MOSFET, InAs-nanowire, Hafnium Oxide, high-k-dielectrics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Instead of planner structure MOS, the gate all around (GAA) nanowireMOS has attracted great attention to the researcher's in recent years [1-3].The multi-gate transistor seems to be very efficient for its larger control on the channel as compared to the planner MOS.The superior electrostatic control of the gate over the channel region and reduction of the short channel effects i.e. sub-threshold slope (SS),drain induced barrier lowering (DIBL)etc. [4-7]is the other better field of the GAA MOS.Of the two structures of the gate all around(GAA) MOS, cylindrical one is better than the rectangular one because of its reduction of the fringing(corner) effects.

Till to date, the cylindrical GAA MOS uses Si-nanowire as the channel and SiO₂ as the gate oxide. In order to improve the performance, nanowires having high electron mobility to obtain higher current as well as gate oxides having high-k dielectrics to attain better gate control [8-11] are desired.

Therefore, researchers constantly search materials to achieve high-performance for cylindrical gate all around MOSFET.

To achieve the better performance in MOS structures (single gate MOSFET, double gate MOSFET, Four Gate MOSFET, FinFET etc.), various materials and oxides are constantly being tested. GaAs, Si-Ge, InAs etc. are employed as the replacement of Si and various high-k dielectrics like Al₂O₃, HfO₂ etc. are used instead of SiO₂. As a channel material InAs is the most suitable, since it has higher electron mobility (up to 30000 cm²/V-s), lower electron effective mass (0.023m₀),higher saturation velocity 2×10⁷ cm/s and low contact resistance.As a gate oxide, HfO₂can be chosen as its dielectric constant is much higherthan that of SiO₂(approximately 3.9 for SiO₂, whereas 15 for HfO₂), for which the gate oxide thickness as well asthe gate leakage current are decreased and the gate capacitance is increased.

A number of works has been found in the literature [12-15] which employed InAs as a channel and HfO₂ as an oxide layer. All these works were carried out for single gate, MOSFETs; none considered these materials for the gate all around structure. This work, therefore, proposes a CGAA structure where InAs nanowire acts as a channel and HfO₂ as a gate oxide for the first time in the literature. Using Silvaco TCAD, this novel structure is tested for its various performance measures. The test results shows significant improvement over the conventional CGAA structure.

II. DEVICE STRUCTURE

This work proposes a structure of a cylindrical gate all around (CGAA) MOSFET. The CGAA uses InAs-nanowire as channel and HfO₂ as the gate oxide. The 3D view of the proposed structure generated by SILVACO TCAD is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 13D radial cross section view of the proposed InAs-channel and HfO₂ based CGAAMOSFET

In Atlas2D, the proposed nanowire transistor structure is simulated using a quasi-3D model. This is done as follows. First, cylindrical symmetry is specified in the mesh-statement. This will cause Atlas to simulate the structure as if its x-direction is the radial direction of a cylinder, with the y-axis at the center of the cylinder, whereas, the y-coordinates increase in the downward direction, with 0 at the top of the structure. The 2D view simulated by Atlas2D is shown in Fig 2.

All the simulations are carried out using Silvaco TCAD. In these simulations Fermi-Dirac statistics is used and field-dependent mobility as well as SRH recombination models are employed. Both Newton and Gummel methods are applied, where automated Newton-Richardson procedure is implemented to speed up the iteration process.

Fig 22D radial cross section view of the proposed InAs-channel and HfO₂ based CGAAMOSFET generated by Atlas2D.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the simulation results carried away by Silvaco TCAD for three channel-oxide combinations of cylindrical gate-all-around MOSFET, namely, InAs-Channel + HfO₂-oxide, InAs-Channel + SiO₂-oxide and Si-Channel + SiO₂-oxide and provide a comparative analysis of these combinations or structures using various figures of merit.

Since InAs has much higher mobility than Si (80000 compared to 1300), therefore a much higher current is expected when Si is replaced with InAs as channel

material. On the other hand, HfO₂ has at least five times higher permittivity than SiO₂, which means MOSFETs with HfO₂ as oxide has higher control over the channel and hence, higher current capability as compared with MOSFETs which use SiO₂ as oxide. All of the Figs3 to 6 presented in this section are very much in agreement with these facts.

Fig 3 Effect of variation of channel radius on the ID vs. VD and ID vs. VG characteristics. Here, the channel length is 200nm, oxide thickness is 4 nm and channel doping level is $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

The effects of the variation of the channel radius on the ID-vs-VD and ID-vs-VG curves have been observed in Fig 3. From these figures, it is evident that as channel radius increases, the drain current increases. It is expected since increase in the channel radius results in lowering of the channel resistance.

Fig4 shows the effect of channel length variation on the IDvsVD and IDvsVG curves. Since increase in channel length causes increase in the channel resistance, a decrease in the drain current is expected when channel length increases. Both these plots of Fig4 reflect this effect.

Fig 4 Effect of variation of the channel length on the ID vs. VD and ID vs. VG characteristics. Here, the channel radius is 10 nm, oxide thickness is 4 nm and channel doping level is $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

The effect of the variation of channel doping is shown in the Fig 5. Since higher doping level causes channel resistance to decrease, drain current should increase with the increase of channel doping. This increase in the drain current with the channel doping has clearly been demonstrated in the Fig 5.

Fig 5 Effect of variation of the channel doping level on the I_D vs. V_D and I_D vs. V_G characteristics. Here, the channel radius is 10 nm, channel length is 200nm and the oxide thickness is 4 nm.

As the gate oxide thickness decreases, the MOS capacitance increases and hence, the control over the MOS increases i.e. MOS exhibits higher drain current. These expected improvements owing to the lowering of the oxide thickness are depicted in Fig 6.

Table 1 tabulates the figures of merit i.e. maximum drain current (I_{max}), maximum transconductance ($g_{m,max}$), on resistance (R_{on}) and inverse subthreshold slope (I_{ss}) for the three CGAA structures discussed in this work. For all these structures, the channel radius is 10 nm, channel length is 200 nm, oxide thickness is 4 nm and channel doping level is $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This table shows that the proposed structure composed of InAs-channel and HfO_2 -gate oxide has the highest $g_{m,max}$ and I_{max} ratio and possesses the lowest on-resistance R_{on} , whereas, inverse sub-threshold slope I_{ss} of the proposed structure is close to 60mV/dec, the theoretical lower limit.

Fig 6 Effect of variation of the oxide thickness (t_{ox}) on the I_D vs. V_D and I_D vs. V_G characteristics. Here, channel radius is 10 nm, channel length is 200nm and channel doping level is $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figures of merit	Si/SiO ₂	InAs/SiO ₂	InAs/HfO ₂
$g_{m,max}$ (mA/ μm)	0.8562	0.75	1.57
I_{max} (mS/ μm)	0.01015	0.164	0.23
R_{on} ($\Omega - \mu\text{m}$)	9927	1929	1382
I_{ss} (mV/dec)	60.5	63.3	67.2

Table 1 Comparison of various figures of merit of the proposed structure with InAs-channel + SiO₂-gate

oxide and Si-channel + SiO₂-gate oxide. Here, the channel radius is 10 nm, channel length is 200nm and channel doping level is $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and the oxide thickness is 4 nm.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, a new structure of CGAA MOS based on InAs channel and HfO₂ gate oxide is proposed. TCAD-based simulations have been carried out to investigate the performance of this structure. InAs-channel and HfO₂-gate oxide based cylindrical gate all around MOSFET. The same simulations are carried out with the same structure but with different materials i.e. InAs-channel+ SiO₂-gate oxide and Si-channel+ SiO₂-gate oxide. Based on the I_D vs V_D and I_D vs V_G curves and also, on the figures of merit such as maximum drain current (I_{max}), maximum transconductance ($g_{m,max}$), on resistance (R_{on}) and inverse subthreshold slope (I_{ss}), the superiority of the proposed structure over the other two has been confirmed.

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